

FIGHT AGAINST DOPING IN SPORTS

Isomiddinova Bonu Sherali kizi

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute Faculty of physical culture

Student of sports activities (Wrestling).

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Abstract. Article in sports present of the day sports in the field important to the problem directed in sports honesty, correctness and olympism principles protection in doing sports field in order puter in legislation to doping against struggle in the activity legal of problems theoretical and organizational - legal aspects and they are in the activity problems illuminated, athletes right rights expand and to doping against struggle activities improvement done to increase directed Suggestions work developed

Key words: Doping, athlete, anti-doping code, doping control, World Anti-Doping Agency, disqualification, sport.

БОРЬБА С ДОПИНГОМ В СПОРТЕ

Аннотация. Статья в современном спорте в области спорта, важной для решения проблемы, направленной на защиту принципов спортивной честности, корректности и олимпизма в занятиях спортом, с целью внесения в законодательство борьбы с допингом в деятельности юридических проблем теоретических и организационных - правовые аспекты и они заключаются в освещении проблем деятельности, расширении прав спортсменов и улучшении деятельности по борьбе с допингом, направленной на увеличение направленных предложений, разработанных работ.

Ключевые слова: Допинг, спортсмен, антидопинговый кодекс, допинг-контроль, Всемирное антидопинговое агентство, дисквалификация, спорт.

Sport has always been an integral part of human life - for a long time people tried to be faster, taller, stronger. However, sport is now not only entertainment that unites peoples and countries, but also a means of political struggle in the international arena. The athlete's body, his physiology, is the aspect of sports that should be focused on. It has become a serious problem in the world of sports, because the physiological capabilities of a person can be controlled from the outside due to pharmacological effects. Doping is not a new phenomenon. History shows that even the ancient Greeks used many substances to enhance athletic performance. Later, with the development of technology, the situation related to doping reached a deplorable level. All sports organizations started trying to fight against it.

Doping in sports is the acceptance and use of various types of pharmacological drugs by athletes. Doping in sports began to be actively used from the end of the 19th century, and the first of them was strychnine, which in small doses had a short-term stimulating effect on athletes, and at the same time, drinking a lot of coffee is known to increase the performance of athletes. lum.

There are a number of unresolved or incompletely resolved issues in the field of doping and the law.

Doping in sports is a normative problem for international law. This problem has not been completely solved, because the system of state penalties for the use of prohibited pharmacological agents, both in international sports and in some countries, is not effective enough or does not exist at all. That is, the laws of some countries do not establish the norms of responsibility and punishment for doping. The concept of "doping" was defined at the International Sports Medicine Congress held in Strasbourg (France) in 1965. According to this definition, doping is the consumption of foreign substances or physiological substances in an abnormal amount in the body, or artificially and unfairly introducing any substance in an unnatural way, to increase the result of the athlete during the competition. Doping is a substance that enhances the mental and physical activity of the body for a short period of time. Due to the cases of poisoning and deaths from doping substances among athletes, the International Olympic Committee has banned doping during sports since 1967 and strictly controls it. installed According to strict legal regulations, athletes who have used doping are banned from competitions even for several years. The word doping is derived from the English words "doping", "dope", which means "to give drugs". Today there are several types of doping substances. Now we will give you information about the 5 most common doping substances in sports.

1. EPO (erythropoietin). Belongs to more cyclical sports: cycling, skiing, biathlon, swimming, etc.
2. Anabolic steroids (testosterone, stanozolol, nandrolone, methenolone). More related to athletics and weightlifting, swimming, skiing, etc.
3. Diuretics, or diuretics (chlorthalidone, acetazolamide, triamterin, furosemide). Mostly belongs to rhythmic gymnastics, figure skating, athletics and weightlifting.
4. Transfusion of blood and blood components. Mostly cycling, athletics, skiing, etc.
5. Neurostimulants, or psychostimulants (cocaine, ephedrine, ecstasy and amphetamines). They belong to almost all sports - from boxing to rhythmic gymnastics.

In 1978, in Paris on physical education and sports, it was emphasized that physical education and sports are the basic rights of every human being. Article 7 of this document defines

doping as having a harmful effect due to the fact that it is dangerous to health and contrary to sports ethics.

The legal fight against doping began in 1989 after the adoption of the Convention against the use of doping in Strasbourg. Its purpose is to ensure the integrity of the competition and the health of the athletes. Convention participants coordinate the activities of their state organizations dealing with doping in sports. In turn, it is the duty of states to adopt appropriate laws that limit the presence and circulation of doping. Countries that are parties to the 1989 Convention assist their sports organizations in raising anti-doping control funds. The Convention has an annex - it contains a list of prohibited types of pharmacological doping and doping methods. This list is updated annually in accordance with the International Olympic Committee's anti-doping list.

The World Anti-Doping Code provides permanent anti-doping measures in all sports.

Every year, the World Anti-Doping Agency does a great job of conducting comprehensive research, compiling a list of prohibited drugs, accrediting laboratories around the world, holding various symposia dedicated to the problem under consideration. The World Anti-Doping Code applies to all areas classified as competitive sport. That is, these are athletes, their coaches, medical personnel who work with athletes participating in competitions, etc. All participants of competitions are obliged to prevent the introduction of prohibited pharmacological substances into their bodies. It is here that the principle of objective responsibility adopted in the World Anti-Doping Code, the Medical Code of the International Olympic Committee and most other anti-doping rules is implemented. According to this principle, non-compliance with anti-doping requirements consists in identifying prohibited substances taken from the athlete or their signs.

Doping control is conducted to determine the fact of doping use. Doping control is the taking and testing of biological samples in order to determine the presence of prohibited substances in the bodies of athletes or the use of prohibited methods of preparation for competitions. In this case, the violation is recorded regardless of the result of the athlete taking doping. Carelessness or ignorance is not important, the most important thing is the result of doping control, which shows the presence of prohibited substances in the body. The doping control program of the World Anti-Doping Agency is implemented by anti-doping commissions. They have the right to take, code and transport samples. Anti-doping commissioners involved in anti-doping control must keep all information confidential and ensure that the doping control procedure is properly followed.

This process is carried out in specially organized places (doping station).

The winners of the competitions will be subject to compulsory testing. Results should be ready within 48 hours. Although doping leads to world-class victories, their results are invalidated.

In conclusion, it is necessary for countries to cooperate with each other, share experience and act together in the process of developing a common policy to eliminate this phenomenon in sports. As a result, one of the main directions of international relations: strengthening of peace and harmony between people of different countries is achieved. Undermining of the main meaning and content of sports will be avoided, a fair mechanism of fight against doping will lead to popularization of Olympics and healthy lifestyle.

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